

Validation of the employability and new ways of working perception scale in Spanish university students

Validación de la escala de percepción sobre empleabilidad y nuevas formas de trabajo en alumnado universitario

Arminda SUÁREZ PERDOMO. Assistant Professor. Universidad de La Laguna, España (asuper@ull.edu.es).

Yaritza GARCÉS DELGADO. Lecturer. Universidad de La Laguna, España (ygarcesd@ull.edu.es).

Carmen Nuria ARBELO ROSALES. Assistant Professor. Universidad de La Laguna, España (carbello@ull.edu.es).

David LÓPEZ AGUILAR. Senior Lecturer. Universidad de La Laguna, España (dlopez@ull.edu.es).

Abstract

Society is in constant change, which has fostered new forms of work mediated by technology. In this context, undergraduates are under great pressure for their future incorporation into the labour market. This study presents the validation of a scale that assesses students' perception of employability and new ways of working, analysing the psychometric properties and the discriminative value in terms of sociodemographic variables and professional competencies. The participants in this study were 584 students from 30 Spanish universities. The factor analysis carried out using the Exploratory Structural Equation Model (ESEM) showed a five-factor structure (fears, professional expectations and competencies, professional planning and development, self-determination expectations and self-management expectations), with adequate psychometric properties. Likewise, the factors show good discrimination with respect to gender, degree, knowledge branch and course. They also show good diagnosticity for the competencies of leadership, organisation and planning, general and basic knowledge of the profession and ICT management. The new scale thus provides relevant information on the perception of employability and new forms of employment among university students.

Keywords: employability, new ways of working, undergraduates, factor analysis, diagnosis.

Resumen

La sociedad está en un constante cambio que ha propiciado nuevas formas de trabajo mediatizadas por la tecnología. En este contexto, el estudiantado universitario se ve sometido a una gran presión de cara a su futura incorporación al mercado laboral. Este estudio presenta

Date of receipt: 08/07/2025

Date of approval: 12/12/2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.9781/rep.2026.392>

Please, cite this article as follows: Suárez Perdomo, A., Garcés Delgado, Y., Arbelo Rosales, C. N. & López Aguilar, D. (2026). Validation of the employability and new ways of working perception scale in Spanish university students [Validación de la escala de percepción sobre empleabilidad y nuevas formas de trabajo en alumnado universitario]. *Revista Española de Pedagogía*, 84(294), 405-423. <https://doi.org/10.9781/rep.2026.392>

la validación de una escala que evalúa la percepción del alumnado sobre la empleabilidad y las nuevas formas de trabajo, analizando las propiedades psicométricas y el valor discriminativo con respecto a variables sociodemográficas y de competencias profesionales. Participaron 584 estudiantes de 30 universidades españolas. El análisis factorial realizado por medio del Modelo de Ecuaciones Estructurales Exploratorio (ESEM) mostró una estructura de cinco factores (miedos, expectativas y competencias profesionales, planificación y desarrollo profesional, expectativas de autodeterminación y expectativas de autogestión), con unas propiedades psicométricas adecuadas. Asimismo, los factores muestran una buena discriminación con respecto al género, la titulación, la rama de conocimiento y el curso. También, presenta una buena diagnosticidad para las competencias de liderazgo, organización y planificación, conocimientos generales y básicos de la profesión y manejo de las TIC. Por tanto, la nueva escala ofrece información relevante sobre la percepción de la empleabilidad y las nuevas formas de empleo en el alumnado universitario.

Palabras clave: empleabilidad, nuevas formas de trabajo, alumnado universitario, análisis factorial, diagnóstico.

1. Introduction

Employability is a multidimensional construct that integrates competencies, personal attributes and contextual opportunities to facilitate labour market insertion (Grosemans *et al.*, 2023). Nevertheless, the concept has received criticism for shifting the responsibility for professional success towards the individual, overlooking structural factors such as the socioeconomic context, gender inequalities, territorial differences or actual access to employment opportunities (Donald *et al.*, 2018; Rätty *et al.*, 2018).

Employability is thus one of the main concerns of university students during their period of study. Securing employment after graduation and obtaining a job commensurate with their qualifications is one of their main objectives. Employability can be understood as a multidimensional construct that integrates a set of knowledge, skills, personal attributes and contextual opportunities that facilitate insertion and permanence in the labour market (Grosemans *et al.*, 2023). However, it is a complex and often criticised concept, as it tends to emphasise individual responsibility for career progression, disregarding structural conditioning factors such as the socioeconomic context, the actual availability of employment or inequalities of origin (Donald *et al.*, 2018; Rätty *et al.*, 2018). In the present study, employability is addressed through the students' self-perception, in order to understand how they interpret their chances of insertion into an increasingly digitised and demanding labour market.

According to human capital theory, education is a form of individual investment aimed at obtaining explicit benefits related to a professional career that ensures increased competitive edge in the labour market (Nimmi *et al.*, 2021). University students perceive employability as their likelihood of success in the labour market; this leads them to a process of self-assessment of their personal attributes and competencies with the intention of identifying areas they can improve during their university training (Ho *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, students are aware of the current labour market challenges and may feel threatened by the competitiveness existing when applying for potential job positions after graduating (Lewis, 2023).

The challenges facing university students have changed in recent years as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic, which affected economies worldwide. In fact, global Gross Domestic Product is estimated to have been affected by 3.5% in 2020, with a loss of 300 million full-time jobs (Padhan & Prabheesh, 2021). However, according to a recent study published

by the Social Observatory of the “La Caixa” Foundation (Currul & Maynou, 2024), people who currently work remotely state that this form of employment offers several benefits for work-life balance.

This global crisis has represented a potential setback to students’ careers, impacting their career aspirations and self-perceptions regarding their employability and professional prospects within the labour sectors related to their degree courses (Tan *et al.*, 2023). In this context, renewed forms of employability have emerged that substantially transform traditional ways of working, with more versatile working hours and spaces, increased use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and greater individual work autonomy. These new ways of working (NWW) allow efficient adaptation to diverse contexts, facilitating communication and collaboration through advanced digital tools (Demerouti *et al.*, 2014; Gephart, 2002). In this case, universities have found themselves needing to redesign their training strategies to integrate digital competencies into their study plans, preparing for a labour and business market increasingly mediated by emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and collaborative ICT-based systems (CYD Foundation, 2024).

The NWW include practices such as teleworking, hybrid working, digital self-employment and flexibility of place and hours (Andrulli and Gerards, 2023). Although these modalities offer autonomy, work-life balance and cost reduction, they are also associated with risks such as isolation, permanent availability, blurring of boundaries between personal and professional life and new forms of precariousness linked to digital platforms (Padhan & Prabheesh, 2021). Understanding this duality is essential for interpreting student perceptions regarding their employment expectations.

However, the integration of ICT in the labour market has not only altered the way tasks are performed, but has also generated new demands that significantly affect university students. These are manifested differently according to gender, branch of knowledge and academic level. According to the 2024 Digital Talent and Employability Report (Rueda *et al.*, 2024), only 23.47% of ICT specialists in Spain are women. This gender gap not only affects representation in technological sectors but also the assumption of leadership roles and the perception of competitiveness in digital working environments (Cáceres *et al.*, 2022), thus favouring the gender-related employment gap. Initiatives such as UNIVERGEM, promoted by the Andalusian Institute for Women, are a prime example of efforts aimed at improving the employability and entrepreneurship of university women, contributing to the reduction of gender gaps. (Instituto Andaluz de la Mujer, 2023). This programme includes training itineraries in entrepreneurship, professional mentoring, personalised advice and support for the launch of business projects led by university women. Complementary initiatives, such as “Women and Digital Talent” or STEAM projects with a gender perspective driven by public universities, contribute to addressing gaps in highly in-demand technology sectors.

Regarding the knowledge branch of university degrees, the CYD 2024 Report highlights that engineering, specifically computer science, shows higher employment rates (>90%), while degrees in Social Sciences and humanities display more vulnerable rates (<50%). This mismatch highlights the need to align educational offerings with labour market demands, promoting the acquisition of transversal competencies such as organisation, planning, leadership and specific skills related to advanced ICT and AI management (CYD Foundation, 2024; Rueda *et al.*, 2024). These employability skills are considered transversal and fundamental for connecting the professional and academic worlds (Rodríguez Moreno, 2010; Álvarez-Pérez *et al.*, 2016). In this sense, developing these skills and understanding the new work dynamics contribute to optimising the employment integration process from university training (Martínez *et al.*, 2019), highlighting the importance of promoting sustainable skills that enable better opportunities to enter and adapt to the professional environment (Alarcón, 2018). Competencies such as leadership, planning and organisation, considered productive, enable a series of improvement scenarios in the workplace that favour the acquisition of attitudes and aptitudes demanded by companies (Hinojo-Lucena *et al.*, 2020). Likewise, another essential competence in today’s society is related to the management of

ICTs, which is of great interest in a society constantly undergoing technological change, and it is essential to assess how future employees know how to adapt to different scenarios, thus increasing productivity and employability levels (Anticona-Hoyos *et al.*, 2024).

Cross-cutting skills represent a set of professional abilities not linked to a specific disciplinary area that facilitate adaptation to various work contexts. Among them are communication, leadership, time management, planning and problem-solving, considered as a bridge between university education and the demands of the contemporary labour market (Martínez and González, 2018). These skills serve as the foundation upon which more specific competencies related to each profession are subsequently developed.

The academic level is also a relevant variable for studying employability perception. According to Rueda *et al.* (2024), competencies related to the advanced use of ICT and specialisation through postgraduate studies are key elements for holding positions or job roles with greater responsibility within companies. In turn, the CYD Foundation (2024) states that specialisation in areas of high labour demand, such as emerging technologies, significantly increases the employment prospects for graduates.

In this context, educational institutions have the responsibility to offer training plans that foster the acquisition of digital and professional skills in their students. Thus, it is essential to recognise that Higher Education institutions can act as agents of transformation within a specific social, economic, professional, educational, etc., context. One example is the study carried out by Passey *et al.* (2021), which noted that the transition towards a hybrid training-work educational model has been a challenge for both teaching staff and students, as it is accompanied by the need for greater digital literacy and a better capacity for adaptation in teaching-learning processes. This has created new opportunities to analyse how students perceive their preparedness and the development of professional competencies for their incorporation and adaptation into an increasingly demanding, changing and digitalised labour market.

It is precisely in this context that the need arises to develop an instrument to gather information on university students' perception of their employability and the NWW. In this sense, the objectives of this work are: 1) to design and validate the Perception Scale on Employability and NWW, identifying the optimal psychometric properties for its use in undergraduate and postgraduate students; and 2) assess the discriminative value through an analysis of individual differences (gender, qualification, course, knowledge area and personal situation) and the diagnostic sensitivity and specificity regarding professional competences (leadership, organisation and planning, general and basic knowledge of the profession and ICT management). In this case, it is essential to analyse the discriminative power with respect to professional competences, given that students are aware of the importance of knowing their level of professional competences in order to understand their employability level (Murthy & Machet, 2021).

2. Method

2.1. Participants

The study employed a non-probabilistic convenience sampling, involving 584 students from 30 Spanish public universities (for example, University of La Laguna, University of Salamanca, University of Santiago de Compostela, University of León, University of the Basque Country, University of Oviedo, etc.), of whom 77.4% were women, 21.9% men, and the remaining 0.7% of other genders. The participants were aged between 17 and 61 years ($M = 22.77$, $SD = 7.15$). Some 85.1% were studying for an undergraduate degree and 14.9% for a postgraduate degree; moreover, 38.4% were in their first year, 17% in their second, 21.6% in their third, 13.7% in their fourth and 9.4% were enrolled in simultaneous subjects from different years. Regarding the branch of knowledge, 64.7% belonged to Social Sciences and Legal Studies, 14.4% to Sciences, 9.8% to Arts and Humanities, 8% to Health Sciences, and the remaining 3.1% to Engineering

and Architecture. Finally, regarding their personal situation, 73.8% were full-time students, 21.2% combined their studies with work, 3.4% had minors in their care, and the remaining 1.5% had an elderly person in their care.

2.2. Instruments

2.2.1. Perception Scale on Employability and NWW in university students

To develop the scale for analysing university students' perception of employability and NWW, the study carried out by Jackson and Tomlinson (2020) was used as a starting point. This study analysed the relationship between career planning, proactivity and employability perceptions among university students concerning the uncertain conditions of the labour market.

Moreover, the work carried out by Gerards *et al.* (2018) analysing how NWW affect job commitment was also reviewed. From the articles reviewed for item identification, the different original factors that were incorporated into the developed questionnaire were extracted, such as the content dimensions. As a starting point, the instruments used by the reviewed studies were translated from English to Spanish and adapted, taking into consideration recommendation D.2. of the *International Test Commission Guidelines* (2010) for adaptation of the items to the Spanish population.

After the translation, a panel of four people was formed, consisting of two experts on the construct of employability and the NWW, as well as two experts in the development of data collection instruments, in both cases researchers from different universities with extensive experience in both the construct and the development of instruments similar to those used in this study. The inter-judge agreement index exceeded 94% in the Kappa analysis for relevance, clarity and appropriateness, leading to final linguistic and conceptual adjustments before the pilot application. Once the results were received, they were reviewed and the items were improved, considering the recommendations made and the logic of their formulation with respect to the Spanish construct. The response system used for the new measure was on a Likert scale from 1 to 7 (1 strongly disagree and 7 strongly agree). Table 1 shows the items resulting from the dimensions that comprise them.

TABLE 1. Relationship between dimensions and items that comprised the developed instrument.

Dimension	Ítem
1 Perceived labour market situation	1.1 I think there is a wide range of working opportunities for those who complete their university studies.
	1.2 I am concerned about the competitiveness that exists today in securing a job.
	1.3 I think that many students finalising their studies will get jobs that are beneath their educational level.
	1.4 I think university students have difficulty accessing employment once they finish their studies.
	1.5 I am concerned about the job insecurity caused by temporary contracts.
	1.6 I am worried about the current labour market situation.

2. Perceived employability	2.1 I believe my skills will be favourably valued by future employers.
	2.2 I believe I will be able to compete with other university graduates for a job.
	2.3 I am confident that I will be able to enter the profession I want after completing my university studies.
3. Professional career management	2.4 I believe I am capable of managing my own professional career.
	3.1 I think every student should be responsible for managing their own professional career.
	3.2 I think I will be able to manage the setbacks that may arise in my professional career.
	3.3 I believe it is important to be able to freely choose one's professional career.
4. Professional career planning	3.4 I believe I am responsible for both my professional success and failure.
	3.5 I often think about how to plan my professional future.
	4.1 I am aware of the professional decisions I must take in the future.
	4.2 I like to know the different job options available to me. .
	4.3 I am making efforts to improve my employability.
5. Proactivity	4.4 I am looking to develop my employability as much as I can.
	5.1 I think it is important to have a professional career.
	5.2 I often think about my professional future.
6. New ways of working	5.3 I would like to advance in my professional career.
	5.4 I would like to set my own working schedule.
	5.5 I would like to decide where to work.
	5.6 I would like to choose my way of working (by objectives, by schedules, etc.)
	6.1 I would like to have a job where I could access all the necessary information from my computer, mobile phone.
	6.2 I would like to be able to contact my work colleagues quickly.
	6.3 I would like to have a job that offered me the possibility of quickly establishing contact with the management team.

2.2.2. Sociodemographic data.

Seven sociodemographic questions were included, indicating: gender (female, male, other), age, university, qualification (undergraduate, postgraduate), course year (first, second, third, fourth, multiple courses simultaneously), knowledge area (Engineering and Architecture, Sciences, Social and Legal Sciences, Arts and Humanities, Health Sciences), as well as personal situation (I am currently working, I currently have minors in my care, I currently have adults in my care, none of the above reflects my current reality).

2.2.3. Professional competencies

Four blocks of professional competencies were included, based on the study by Martínez Clares y González Morga (2018), analysing the level of mastery that university students believe they have in leadership, organisation and planning (ordering and structuring ideas appropriately, managing and administering time correctly, having a proactive attitude, discerning what is important from what is a priority), general and basic knowledge of the profession, and ICT skills. For this purpose, a 7-point Likert scale was used (1 No mastery, 7 High mastery).

2.2.4. Procedure

Prior to dissemination of the scale, approval was obtained from the Ethics and Animal Welfare Research Committee of the University of La Laguna (reference: CEIBA2024-3450). Dissemination of the scale was carried out by contacting the management teams of the centres and departments of the 30 participating universities. The aim was for both the centre and department managements to share with their affiliated teaching staff the email inviting, in turn, the lecturer to distribute the questionnaire to the students through communication mechanisms, whether email or virtual classrooms, etc. To comply with ethical procedures, participant anonymity was ensured in accordance with the Organic Law 3/2018, of 5 December, on Personal Data Protection and Guarantee of Digital Rights.

2.2.5. Data analysis

To respond to the first objective and find the factorial structure of the scale, the Exploratory Structural Equation Modelling (ESEM, Asparouhov and Muthén, 2009) was used. This model has a series of advantages listed below: (1) it combines Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), taking into account the variance-covariance matrices; (2) the MESE model is the one that best fits the measurement, as it is a Likert scale; (3) the calculation of fit indices and correlations between latent variables is more precise, as the factorial weight of the items in other factors does not need to be zero.

In addition, the Geomin oblique rotation method was used, as it involves oblique rotations that show relationships between factors that are based on constructs closer to the reality of the scale when applied to the Social Sciences (Brown, 2006; Schmitt, 2011). The Weighted Least Squares estimation method was also used, which adjusts for Mean and Variance (WLSMV, Weighted Least Squares Mean and Variance Adjusted).

For the analysis of fit of the resulting model, the indicators of the χ^2 test, the X^2/df ratio, the RMSEA index, the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Weighted Root Mean Square Residual (WRMR) were used. A good model fit is considered when the TLI/CFI indexes reach values above .90 and the RMSEA index is in the .08-.05 range. (Byrne, 2013). In addition, we used Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO, Pérez and Medrano, 2010).

Following the analyses, the optimal number of factors had to be decided according to the results obtained. To this end, the following criteria were considered: (1) their theoretical

sense, analysing the thematic coherence of the item content; (2) the existence of a number of factors with at least three items in each factor and which were significant ($NC = 95\%$) only in one or two factors; (3) finally, the goodness of fit indices were observed, since relying on this criterion alone may lead to accepting more factors than necessary (Choi *et al.*, 2007).

After determining the optimal number of factors for the measurement, factorial weights below .30 were discarded, as were those where a difference in weights between two factors of less than .15 was observed. Subsequently, the internal consistency of the scale and the different factors that make up the measure were analysed, finding McDonald's Omega coefficient (McDonald, 2013). Finally, it was verified that each factor measured different constructs with an analysis of repeated measures (MANOVA).

To respond to the second objective and verify variability in individual scores, mean contrasts (ANOVA) were performed with: gender, degree, year, field of study and personal situation. The effect size (ES) indicator used was the η^2 statistic (Cohen and Swerdlik, 2006). Likewise, to ascertain the discriminative capacity, taking into account the sensitivity and specificity of the scale, the ROC curve was used. The professional competencies variables were: leadership, organisation and planning, general and basic professional knowledge, and ICT management. This analysis shows the sensitivity/specificity of the groups, previously identifying 0.33% and 0.66% of the sample to indicate the extreme pairs in each of the items. On the Y-axis of coordinates is sensitivity, which is calculated from the group with the positive value (high command of professional competencies) and on the X-axis is the fraction with the negative value (low command of professional competencies). A curve of .50 indicates non-discriminatory, samples from .60 to .90 indicate a moderate accuracy of the test (Cerdeira and Cifuentes, 2012). The optimal cutoff point produces maximum sensitivity, specificity and area under the curve (AUC). For the descriptive statistics, contrast and ROC Curve, SPSS v26 was used; for the MESE, Mplus 8.4 (Muthén and Muthén, 2013), and finally, to estimate McDonald's Omega coefficient, Microsoft Excel was utilised.

3. Results

3.1. Psychometric analysis of the Perception of Employability and NWW scale in university students

To address the first objective, a model fit analysis was conducted to determine the number of factors that make up the developed measure. As observed in Table 2, the factorial structure where at least three significant items coincide in one factor and are only significant in one or more factors is the five-factor solution. Thus, if the number of factors is further increased to six or seven, the model fit index improves, but an optimal number of items is not observed in each of the identified factors, with less discrimination in this regard. However, it was observed that in the five-factor model the model fit was adequate, so it was decided that this solution was the most suitable. In addition, in the five-factor solution, the KMO test yielded a value of .907 and Bartlett's sphericity test was significant (8433.385, df 378, $p < .000$). Finally, an internal reliability analysis of the five-factor model was performed using McDonald's Omega coefficient with a value of .91, with .78 for the first factor, .82 for the second, .89 for the third, .83 for the fourth, and .86 for the fifth.

TABLE 2. Number of factors with three significant (95%) items in one factor and not significant in more than one or two factors and fit indices of each resulting model.

Factors	Fact/items	X2	gl	RMSEA	90%	CFI	TLI	WRMR
2	2	1185.752	207	.090	.085-.095	.84	.79	.044
3	3	981.195	186	.086	.080-.091	.87	.81	.037
4	4	575.763	166	.065	.059-.071	.93	.89	.031
5	5	416.245	147	.056	.050-.062	.96	.92	.024
6	5	313.9.7	129	.050	.043-.057	.97	.94	.021
7	5	240.259	112	.044	.037-.052	.98	.95	.018

Note: Fact/Items = number of factors with three or more significant items (95%) on one factor and not significant on more than one or two factors.

The factorial solution obtained comprised five factors, with factor loadings ranging from .334 to 1.006, as shown in Table 3, selecting, for this purpose, the STDYX standardisation estimation of the resulting CFA model which obtained a significance of $p \leq .001$. The first factor, designated Fears, of five items; the second factor, Professional expectations and competencies, consists of eight items; the third factor, named Professional planning and development, consists of eight items; the fourth factor, Self-determination expectations, consists of three items; lastly, the fifth factor, Self-management expectations, consists of three items. Finally, a repeated measures analysis (MANOVA) was conducted to verify whether the factors measured different constructs. In this way, a significant effect was observed, indicating a difference between them with a large effect size ($F(4,580) = 450.34, p < .001, \eta^2 = .76$). The highest scores were shown by the Self-determination expectations factor, and the lowest scores by the Professional expectations and competencies factor.

TABLE 3. Factor weights for the final version of the scale according to the Standardised 5-factor model

Item	Factors				
	Fears	Professional expectations and competences	Professional planning and development	Self-determination expectations	Self-management expectations
1	-.125	.399	-.028	.050	-.029
2	.539	-.021	-.009	.053	.084
3	.444	.048	.042	.064	-.004
4	.676	.004	.007	-.061	.036
5	.733	-.002	-.004	-.005	-.035
6	.758	-.002	.099	.008	.003

7	-.057	.645	-.061	.008	-.010
8	.099	.570	-.060	.107	-.029
9	-.096	.664	.021	-.005	.036
10	.031	.744	.022	-.048	.064
11	.079	.638	.038	.002	-.038
12	-.064	.667	-.097	.156	.153
13	.055	.540	.281	.130	.177
14	-.005	.445	.072	-.066	-.029
15	-.088	-.066	.916	.003	.038
16	.051	.252	.552	.040	.071
17	.040	.035	.527	.167	-.043
18	.012	.128	.655	-.001	.004
19	.000	.077	.692	-.016	.169
20	.037	.178	.334	-.017	.002
21	-.009	-.013	.889	.012	.077
22	.056	.053	.507	.106	-.047
23	-.029	.054	.003	.774	.206
24	.186	-.011	.027	.507	.064
25	.002	-.016	-.012	.889	.029
26	-.007	-.031	.039	.261	.512
27	-.007	.006	-.047	-.013	1.006
28	.009	.004	.076	.101	.753

3.2. Variability of individual scores and discriminatory capacity of the new scale

To address the final objective, analyses of variance (ANOVA) were first conducted between the factors and sociodemographic variables. The significant differences observed in each of the factors are identified below.

Factor 1. Fears. Regarding this first factor, significant differences were observed in gender ($F(2,581)=8.78$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.03$); the analysis showed differences between women ($M = 5.62$, $SD = 1.1$) and men ($M = 5.21$, $SD = 1.1$). Differences were also found concerning the branch of knowledge ($F(4,579)=5.44$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.04$); in this case, the differences are shown between students of Social Sciences ($M = 5.57$, $SD = 1.0$), Arts and Humanities ($M = 5.60$, $SD = 1.0$), and Health Sciences ($M = 5.80$, $SD = .74$) with respect to the scores obtained by those in Engineering and Architecture ($M = 4.58$, $SD = .95$).

Factor 2. Professional expectations and competences. In the case of the second factor, significant differences were identified regarding the degree ($F(1,582)=5.63$, $p<.01$, $\eta^2=.01$), as postgraduate students ($M = 4.66$, $SD = .75$) scored higher than undergraduate students ($M = 4.43$, $SD = .85$). Significant differences were also observed in terms of the course ($F(4,539)=2.48$, $p<.05$, $\eta^2=.01$), although no differences were found in the *post hoc* among the groups. Finally, significant differences were observed in terms of the knowledge branch ($F(4,579)=2.44$, $p<.05$, $\eta^2=.01$), although again no differences were found in the *post hoc* analysis among the groups.

Factor 3. Professional planning and development

Regarding the third factor, significant differences were observed in gender ($F(2,581)=4.05$, $p<.05$, $\eta^2 = .01$), as the women ($M = 5.86$, $DT = 1.0$) achieved a higher score than the men ($M = 5.59$, $SD = 1.0$). Significant differences were also found in the degree ($F(1,582)=9.12$, $p<.01$, $\eta^2=.02$), as postgraduate students ($M = 6.10$, $SD = .89$) scored higher than undergraduates ($M = 5.74$, $DT = 1.01$).

Factor 4. Self-determination expectations. For the fourth factor, significant differences were observed in terms of the degree ($F(1,582)=3.85$, $p<.05$, $\eta^2=.01$), since postgraduate students ($M = 6.22$, $SD = .87$) scored higher than undergraduates ($M = 5.97$, $SD = 1.1$). Moreover, significant differences were found with respect to the knowledge branch ($F(4,579)=3.45$, $p<.01$, $\eta^2=.02$); in this case, it was observed that the students from Health Sciences ($M = 4.73$, $SD=.69$) obtained a higher score than those from Science ($M = 5.84$, $SD = 1.2$) and Social Sciences ($M = 5.99$, $SD = 1.0$).

Factor 5. Self-management expectations. Finally, regarding the fifth factor, significant differences were found with respect to gender ($F(2,581) =7.08$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.03$), with women scoring higher ($M = 6.10$, $SD = 1.1$) than men ($M = 5.67$, $SD = 1.3$).

Secondly, an ROC curve was performed using professional competencies variables: leadership, organisation and planning, general and basic knowledge of the profession and ICT management. For this purpose, two classification levels were established based on the percentiles .33 and .66; with "low" being those scores below .33 and "high" those scores above .66 in each of the variables for subsequent analysis. The factors resulting from the new scale were used as a diagnostic measure. The ROC curve analysis (Figure 1, 2, 3 and 4) by obtaining the area under the curve (AUC) showed moderate accuracy with respect to leadership according to the factors: Professional expectations and competencies, Professional planning and development, and Self-management expectations. Likewise, moderate accuracy was identified concerning organisation and planning in terms of the factors: Fears, Professional expectations and competencies, Professional planning and development, and Self-management expectations. Finally, moderate accuracy was found regarding general and basic knowledge of the profession and the use of ICT in terms of the factors: Professional expectations and competencies, Professional planning and development, and Self-management expectations.

FIGURE 1. ROC analysis of the AUC of the Perception on Employability and NWW factors according to leadership.

FIGURE 2. ROC analysis of the AUC of the Perception on Employability and NWW factors according to organisation and planning.

FIGURE 3. ROC analysis of the AUC of the Perception on Employability and NWW factors according to general and basic knowledge of the profession.

FIGURE 4. ROC analysis of the AUC of the Perception on Employability and NWW factors according to ICT management.

4. Discussion

The objectives of this study were to develop and identify the psychometric properties of the Employability and NWW Perception Scale for Undergraduate and Postgraduate University Students, as well as to verify its discriminative value using individual differences analysis and diagnostic capacity, considering variables such as gender, degree, knowledge branch and academic year, along with professional competencies (leadership, organisation and planning, general and basic professional knowledge and ICT management). Regarding the first objective, the Scale of Perception of Employability and NWW among undergraduate and postgraduate university students was developed, based on the works carried out by Gerards *et al.* (2018) and Jackson and Tomlinson (2020). The results showed an optimal five-factor solution: Fears, Expectations and professional competencies, Professional planning and development, Self-determination expectations and Self-management expectations. A scale was obtained that gathers the necessary information to understand university students' perception of their employability and NWW. This scale provides valuable information on self-perceived competency, students' perceptions of employability, and potential adaptability to flexible work environments. (Monteiro *et al.*, 2020; Tan *et al.*, 2023).

The first factor, Fears, analyses the main concerns students have about uncertainty in their future careers, competitiveness and the labour market situation. This first factor refers to the challenges university students currently face, as they are aware of the importance of self-assessment to consider their capabilities for entering an uncertain labour market, with high competition for employment for which they have trained during their undergraduate and/or postgraduate years (Nimmi *et al.*, 2021; Lewis, 2023). The second factor, Professional expectations and competencies, assesses the skills that must be acquired during their years of study to advance their professional careers, taking into account self-expectations for achieving a successful professional career in the future. In other words, this factor analyses the notion of job stability and social status that students aspire to, believing that by acquiring professional skills during their training process, they are guaranteeing their effective inclusion in the current labour market (Aranda *et al.*, 2021; Hernández Campos *et al.*, 2013). The third factor, Professional planning and development, refers to the future planning undertaken by students during their training period, in an attempt to understand the job options available to them and to improve their employability. In this sense, they perceive how they are constructing their own employability; analysing the attributes and competencies that will lead them to future professional success (Ho *et al.*, 2023).

The fourth and fifth factors relate to NWW, which have become increasingly prominent in recent years following COVID-19 (Andrulli and Gerards, 2023). Specifically, the fourth factor, Expectations of self-determination, emphasises the ability to set flexible working hours, location and working methods. In the current context, NWW allow for a more flexible traditional work, breaking down the barriers of the workplace, spaces and schedules with the aid of ICT and providing greater working autonomy (Demerouti *et al.*, 2014; Gephart, 2002). The current crisis situation has led to changes in the world of work, and university students are becoming aware of these changes and the possibilities that this new labour paradigm opens up (Pataki-Bittó & Kapusy, 2021; Tan *et al.*, 2023). Finally, the fifth factor, Self-management expectations, refers to the ability to have all information available on the computer, being able to work from home and offering the possibility of organising and contacting the team without needing to be physically close, but rather by using ICT as a tool for work and contact. Benefits of remote working were observed, such as savings achieved by not having to travel to work, the elimination of unproductive meetings, fewer sick days and breaks or lower workplace organisation costs (Pokojski *et al.*, 2022).

Regarding the second objective, an optimal discriminative capacity of the scale is observed, according to individual analyses, since this version of the scale can provide valuable information about employability and new gender perspectives among university students, by noting the significant differences it shows in this variable. It is perceived that, regarding gender, women show more fears in Professional planning and development and in Self-management

expectations. Gender can offer an important dimension to the debate on employability and NWW, as university-educated women tend to be less inclined to take control of their own careers through professional guidance with the same confidence as their male peers (Donald *et al.*, 2018). Thus, this scale could contribute to the analysis of the self-perception of women studying university degrees regarding their employability, improving self-awareness of their entrepreneurial capabilities and contributing to the reduction of gender gaps in university (Instituto Andaluz de la Mujer, 2023). Although the scale was not specifically designed for gender differentiation, the results obtained indicate that it could be used in future studies that examine the self-perception of leadership, professional confidence and self-determination in university women, especially in STEM fields and digitised work environments.

Furthermore, a clear differentiation is observed in the self-perception of employability and NWW based on the field of knowledge or academic level, which is highly relevant for understanding firsthand in which areas of learning or at what stage of undergraduate or postgraduate training students are aware of the importance of employability and the NWW that exist in contemporary society. This will help students feel that they meet expectations by becoming competitive future employees, acquiring the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to effectively enter the current labour market (Groseman *et al.* 2023).

Finally, an adequate discriminatory value regarding professional competencies is observed. The scale was demonstrated to be capable of measuring the perception of employability based on competences such as leadership, planning and organisation, basic and general knowledge of the profession and the use of ICT. It was also demonstrated that this scale will allow measuring the perceptions of university students on a set of competencies related to employability and NWW, and how these competencies could help describe the profile of the students in terms of their future incorporation into the working world (Murthy & Machet, 2021). As one of the main functions of the university today is to prepare future graduates to be effectively included in the labour market (Daniels and Booker, 2014), having a scale that provides valid information on the employability skills students are acquiring and how it can be related to students' own perceptions of employability and their ability to adapt to NWW will possibly contribute to improving the ability to manage a successful career path (Rätty *et al.*, 2018).

This study has limitations that should be addressed in future research. First, the sample is a convenience sample, as emails were sent to universities that were considered likely to participate, but no type of probabilistic sampling was used. Secondly, the data were taken from a self-report questionnaire which, even considering the level of reliability shown, possible biases in data acquisition such as social desirability, or the possible interpretation by the respondent based on their self-perception of what is being asked, should be taken into account. Despite the results obtained, it is important to recognise that the scale measures individual perceptions, but does not take into account structural factors that influence labour market integration, such as economic, territorial or gender inequalities. Therefore, its use must be complemented with contextual information that allows the results to be interpreted from a broader perspective and avoid exclusively individualising approaches.

Nevertheless, the design and validation of the new scale significantly contributes to advancing knowledge in educational and occupational research, providing a practical tool for Higher Education institutions to develop specific training and support strategies. In this way, it is expected that future studies will analyse university students' perceptions regarding professional competencies and labour market demands. These results could promote better preparation of university students to face the challenges of a digitised and competitive labour market, reducing inequalities and encouraging a more equitable and effective professional transition.

In conclusion, an instrument sensitive to the analysis of a construct that needs to be explored among university students is presented. Allowing, in turn, the identification of professional competencies acquired by this student body in the training process, addressing the labour and technological demands of contemporary society.

Author contributions

Arminda Suárez Perdomo. Conceptualization, data analysis, draft writing, review.

Yaritza Garcés Delgado. Conceptualization, draft writing, review.

Carmen Nuria Arbelo Rosales. Conceptualization, review.

David López Aguilar. Conceptualization, review.

AI Statement

The authors declare that they have not used artificial intelligence (AI) in the preparation of this article.

Funding

The authors declare that they have received financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article. This work was funded by the University of La Laguna through the Own Research Plan 2023 within the framework of the Call for Expressions of Interest for Projects Led by Early-Career Researchers, File No. 2023/2320 ASP.

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Author biographies

Arminda Suárez-Perdomo. Assistant Professor in Research Methods and Diagnosis in Education at the University of La Laguna. Doctor of Psychology with international distinction and extraordinary doctoral award. She is a member of the Family and Human Development (FADE) and Multidisciplinary Educational Research (MUINED) research groups affiliated with the ULL. Regional Delegate in the Canary Islands for the Interuniversity Association for Pedagogical Research (AIDIPE). Her lines of research focus on the inappropriate use of the Internet and social networks among secondary school and university students, and its possible relationship with academic performance, academic goals, decision-making processes, and the development and validation of scales.

 <https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0002-6755-5284>

Yaritza Garcés-Delgado. Lecturer at the University of La Laguna, Faculty of Education, in Research Methods and Diagnosis in Education. She is a member of two established research groups: the University Group for Integrated Training and Guidance (GUFOI) and the Multidisciplinary Group for Educational Research (MUINED). She is secretary of the Canary Islands Regional Delegation of the Interuniversity Association for Pedagogical Research (AIDIPE). Her main lines of research are a) academic and professional guidance; b) emerging technologies in higher education; and c) lines and methods of research in education; adaptation and validation of scales.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3471-1014>

Carmen Nuria Arvelo Rosales. Assistant Professor attached to the Department of Didactics and Educational Research at the University of La Laguna. She is a member of two established research groups: the Diversity Research Group (GIED) and the Multidisciplinary Educational Research Group (MUINED). Her research work has focused on the development of teaching skills, initial teacher training, educational inclusion and attention to diversity. She has published in scientific journals and participated in numerous national and international conferences and scientific events.

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7786-3814>

David López Aguilar. Senior Lecturer at the University of La Laguna. He belongs to the University Group for Integrated Training and Guidance (GUFOI) at the same university. His research focuses on students' adaptation to university education, the development of generic skills, the analysis of factors involved in dropping out and prolonging university education, and the educational and professional development of high-level athletes. He has published books, chapters and articles and has participated in national and regional research and innovation projects. He has been the principal investigator in a project funded by the Ministry of Science and Innovation on university dropout rates.

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4460-1954>